

6G4SOCIETY

D4.1 COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION STRATEGY AND PLAN

Revision: v.1.0

Work package WP 4

Task 4.1

Due date 30/04/2024

Submission date 26/04/2024

Deliverable lead Digital4Planet

Version 1.6

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Abstract This deliverable aims to develop a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy for 6G4Society for outreach and impact creation, taking into account the results to be disseminated, the target groups and audiences, and the impact to be achieved. Expected outcomes and impacts, evaluation measures and tools are also defined. This strategy provides the framework for the various awareness-raising, promotional and community-building activities that will be carried out during the project.

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Co-funded by
the European Union

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER,
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Keywords Communication, Dissemination

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Description of change	List of contributor(s)
V1.0	06/03/2024	1st version of the template for comments	Matilde Voltolini (D4P)
V1.1	18/03/2024	50% of content written sent for internal review	Sophie Staheyeff (D4P)
V1.2	20/03/2024	Quality Assurance review	Giota Lilli (eBOS)
V1.3	09/04/2024	100% of content written sent for internal review	Sophie Staheyeff (D4P), Matilde Voltolini (D4P), Rosie McDonald (D4P)
V1.4	22/04/2024	Integration of comments from internal reviewers (eBOS and NOVA)	Sophie Staheyeff (D4P)
V1.5	25/04/2024	Integration of comments from internal reviewers (eBOS and NOVA), final formatting	Sophie Staheyeff (D4P)

DISCLAIMER

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
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Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

6G4SOCIETY project has received funding from the [Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking \(SNS JU\)](#) under the European Union's [Horizon Europe research and innovation programme](#) under Grant Agreement No 101139070. This work has received funding from the [Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation \(SERI\)](#).

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Note: This deliverable has only been submitted and is waiting for final approval from the European Commission.

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Nature of the deliverable:	R — Document, report	
Dissemination Level		
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page)	✓

SEN	<i>Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement</i>	
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* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc.

DMP: Data management plan

ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues.

SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable aims to develop a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy for 6G4Society for outreach and impact creation, taking into account the results to be disseminated, the target groups and audiences, and the impact to be achieved. Expected outcomes and impacts, evaluation measures and tools are also defined. This strategy provides the framework for the various awareness-raising, promotional and community-building activities that will be carried out during the project.

Section 2 covers the project vision, the objectives of the strategy, the target audience the project aims to reach and the main messages and activities to engage them, and how 6G4Society aims to communicate and disseminate project results in a way that is respectful of the environment.

Section 3 presents the project's brand identity and how it will ensure a recognisable and consistent visibility throughout its activities and channels. The internal communication channels of the project as well as the external online and offline communication channels and activities are also described in this section. This includes the website, the social media channels, the digital digest, the press releases, events, promotional material, publications and the promotion of the citizens' survey and the information package.

6G4Society being an integral part of the SNS JU ecosystem, Section 4 delves into the synergies that will be cultivated within SNS JU as well as other relevant initiatives to amplify the project's message and grow its reach and relevance.

The final section (Section 5) presents the Key Performance Indicators related to communication and dissemination, the relevant deliverables and milestones as well as a risk assessment and mitigation strategy.

The deliverable wraps up with a list of main conclusions and next steps.

In Appendix A, you will find the project's brand guidelines and the first press release. This illustrates further the activities carried out by 6G4Society as well as the aesthetic the project aims to achieve.

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ABBREVIATIONS

5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G4S	6G4Society
6G-IA	6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
D	Deliverable
DG	Directorate-General
EC	European Commission
ETHICNET	International Workshop on Value-driven Ethical Networking in 6G
ESEE	European Society for Ecological Economics
EU	European Union
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEI	Higher education institution
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KSI	Key Sustainability Indicator
KVI	Key Value Indicator
M	Month
MWC	Mobile World Congress
PSCE	Public Safety Communications Europe Forum
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
SNS JU	European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

1 INTRODUCTION

In the development of 6G technology, there is an existing tension between on the one hand securing technology performance objectives, and on the other ensuring that societal and sustainable values are properly embedded into technology. An added layer of complexity to this comes from the amount of misinformation and fear that came with the roll-out of 5G at the beginning of the decade. Having a robust communication strategy to increase social acceptance of this new generation of connectivity is an essential element of the work of the 6G4Society (6G4S) project.

This deliverable is produced as part of Work Package 4 (WP4) "Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Standardisation" and aims to develop a comprehensive communication and dissemination strategy for 6G4S for outreach and impact creation, taking into account the results to be disseminated, the target groups and audiences, and the impact to be achieved. Expected outcomes and impacts, evaluation measures and tools are also defined. This strategy provides the framework for the various awareness-raising, promotional and community-building activities that will be carried out during the project.

The purpose of this document is, therefore to outline a comprehensive communication and dissemination plan for achieving the following objectives:

- 🔄 Identify target audiences, including a broad range of stakeholders in the European telecommunications community and more specifically the European Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) ecosystem.
- 🔄 Outline the methods, tools, and promotional materials to be used in the dissemination of the project and communication activities.
- 🔄 Provide an overview of the planned activities and list possible opportunities to be exploited within the project.
- 🔄 Define the methodology and procedures to be used in the implementation, monitoring, and evaluation of all communication and dissemination activities.

This is a 'living' document that will be updated with any necessary adjustments during the implementation of the project. The dissemination planning will therefore be constantly assessed and revised during the course of the project. Important updates will be included in the regular reports.

2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The following section will cover the project vision, the objectives of the strategy, the target audiences the project aims to reach, and the main messages and activities to engage them, and how 6G4S aims to communicate and disseminate the project results in a way that is respectful of the environment.

2.1 THE PROJECT VISION

The 6G4S project aims to address the tension between two parallel needs in the technological development of 6G: on the one hand, securing technology performance objectives, and on the other ensuring that societal and sustainable values are properly embedded into the technology.

To achieve this, 6G4S will engage key stakeholders within the SNS JU ecosystem, civil society players, regulators, policy makers, media, and the public at large, to ensure correct and clear information about the expected impacts of 6G technology. Drawing on the fields of ethics, legal and social science and humanities, the project will also provide methods, models, guidelines, policy options, and operation recommendations to develop sustainable and socially accepted 6G technology and applications. The final products 6G4S will develop are a Technology Acceptance Model for 6G, a framework of Key Sustainability Indicators, a policy brief and an operation brief, which will, in turn, be validated by and disseminated through all SNS JU projects.

The main objectives of 6G4S are the following:

- Generating a better understanding and shared knowledge of the aspects influencing public acceptance of 6G technologies.
- Supporting the development of a European Union (EU) consensus framework for a value-based, sustainable, and ethics-driven approach towards 6G and its subsequent promotion through the 6G EU and global standard-setting process.
- Engaging and reaching out to public audiences to build 6G social acceptance.
- Empowering the 6G community to reflect EU policy and legislation into technology solutions for future networks' development and services.

2.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STRATEGY

Key goals of 6G4S are to promote acceptance of 6G in the general public, to understand potential obstacles to it, and to spread correct and adapted information about the technology and its development to European citizens. Communication is therefore a critical part of the project activities and plays an essential role in all WPs.

The main objectives of this communication and dissemination strategy are the following:

- Ensure broad visibility and raise awareness about 6G4S, spreading knowledge about the project and its results, establishing a distinctive and recognisable identity that will support marketing efforts.
- Reach, stimulate, and engage a critical mass of relevant stakeholders to ensure that:

- 6G4S activities are effectively and properly disseminated to the targeted audiences for maximum participation and promotion;
 - correct information about the development of 6G reaches European citizens;
 - the results of the project are effectively showcased, leading to the validation and use of the end products by the relevant stakeholders.
- Ensure close collaboration with the SNS JU programme and projects, while establishing liaisons with relevant initiatives in research and innovation domains such as 6G-IA, 5G AA, 5G-ACIA, one6G, ADRA, as appropriate.

2.3 TARGET AUDIENCE

The following table presents the main target audiences, key messages towards them, and the planned outreach.

TABLE 1: TARGET AUDIENCES, KEY MESSAGES AND PLANNED OUTREACH

Target audience	Key messages	Outreach activities
General public	<p>Information about the current development of 6G, what are the foreseen societal and environmental influences the technology could potentially have.</p> <p>Collection of their hopes and concerns about 6G.</p>	Engagement through project website, press coverage, digital digest, social media, explanatory materials / informative package, involvement in citizen's survey.
Multipliers (civil society organisations/consumers associations/media)	Information about the current development of 6G, what are the foreseen societal and environmental influences the technology could potentially have on their target groups.	Press and media communications, project website, social media, digital digest, publications in dedicated press, organisation of and participation at domain-focused events, direct collaboration for promotion of citizens' survey.
Scientific / Research Community	<p>Information about how European citizens perceive 6G.</p> <p>Information about the foreseen societal and environmental influences 6G could potentially have.</p>	Participation to events, scientific publications, involvement of experts in understanding the impact of 6G on society.

Governments and policymakers	<p>Information about how European citizens perceive 6G.</p> <p>Information about the foreseen societal and environmental influences 6G could potentially have.</p> <p>Guidance on how to integrate societal and environmental values into 6G-related policy, and how to use policy as a leverage for public acceptance (Technology Acceptance Model).</p>	Participation to events, engagement in 6G4S open forums and structured dialogues, presentation and dissemination of final products.
Industry, SMEs and startups	<p>Information about how European citizens perceive 6G.</p> <p>Guidance on how to integrate societal and environmental values into 6G technologies.</p>	Participation to events, presentation of final products, participation at innovation events in EU presenting 6G4Society results.
Standardisation bodies	<p>Information about how European citizens perceive 6G.</p> <p>Information about the foreseen societal and environmental influences 6G could potentially have.</p> <p>Guidance on how to integrate societal and environmental values into 6G-related policy, and how to use policy as leverage for public acceptance (Technology Acceptance Model).</p>	Participation to events, scientific publications.

2.4 SUSTAINABLE APPROACH TO COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION

The 6G4S communication and dissemination approach actively considers the sustainability principles for the organisation of events, and the production of communication materials. For this purpose, 6G4S will:

- Organise, whenever possible, virtual meetings and workshops instead of face-to-face events.

- ↪ Avoid using material resources where possible (avoiding printing flyers when unnecessary and promoting the online download, producing promotional materials using recycled materials, and avoiding single-use products, for example).
- ↪ Encourage the reduction of emissions through sustainable mobility practices (e.g., recommending bicycle use and public transport at 6G4S events, and rewarding these actions).
- ↪ Work with suppliers (printers, caterers, etc.) that use sustainable products and materials.

3 LAUNCHING THE COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

The following section will present 6G4S’ brand identity and how it will ensure a recognisable and consistent visibility throughout its activities and channels. The internal communication channels of the project will also be described. Two longer parts pertaining to the online communication (including the website, the social media channels, the digital digest and the press releases) and the offline communication (including events, promotional material, publications and the promotion of the citizens’ survey and the information package) conclude this section.

3.1 BRAND IDENTITY

As a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) project co-funded by the European Commission (EC), a clear brand identity for the project has been established to ensure consistent visibility in our communication and dissemination activities. Being a CSA within the SNS JU, the [6G SNS Communication and Brand guidelines](#) lay an essential foundation for 6G4S’ brand identity, colour palette, and typography.

The recognition and perception of a brand is highly influenced by its visual presentation. The visual identity of a project is the overall image of its communication. An effective visual brand identity is achieved through the consistent use of certain visual elements that allow for differentiation, such as certain fonts, colours, and graphic elements.

The visual identity and guidelines were established at the initial stage of the project to ensure a strong and unique brand. They will be integrated into all promotional and dissemination materials produced during the project and will be used by all project partners in their communication activities. As a project within the SNS JU, the colours, fonts and logo have all been aligned with those from the guidelines. This ensures a consistent visual support that links to the bigger SNS JU ecosystem and projects. An overview of the visual identity can be found in Appendix A as well as in the following Figure.

FIGURE 1: 6G4S’ VISUAL IDENTITY

3.2 INTERNAL COMMUNICATION

Several internal communication tools have been adopted in order to keep partners informed on processes, and ensure that they keep track of tasks and deadlines easily. The aim is to have everyone up to speed and able to access the required assets, while avoiding any unnecessary information overload. To this purpose, the internal communication tools described in this section were set up.

3.2.1 Mailing lists

Several mailing lists were set up to facilitate 6G4S's internal communication:

TABLE 2: 6G4S INTERNAL MAILING LISTS

Mail	Purpose
all@6G4Society.eu	For general communication such as meeting organisation or reporting purposes.
admin@6G4Society.eu	Including administrative (legal, financial) contacts for topics such as periodic payment or Consortium Agreement signature.

3.2.2 Project internal repository and collaboration tool

Google Drive was selected to act as the main venue to archive and internally exchange all projects' files (including reporting documents, presentations, and graphic assets).

Name	Last modified	File size
6G4Society - External		
Admin, Monitoring, Reporting	9 Jan 2024 Valentina Marga...	—
Meetings	14 Jan 2024 Eva Hajdok	—
Official Documents	9 Jan 2024 Valentina Marga...	—
Submitted deliverables	28 Feb 2024 Eva Hajdok	—
Submitted Proposal	7 Aug 2023 Angelos Alexop...	—
Templates	9 Jan 2024 Valentina Marga...	—
WP1	19 Jan 2024 Eva Hajdok	—
WP2	19 Jan 2024 Eva Hajdok	—
WP3	19 Jan 2024 Eva Hajdok	—
WP4	15 Jan 2024 me	—

FIGURE 2: 6G4S' INTERNAL REPOSITORY GOOGLE DRIVE

The mechanisms that will be used throughout the project in order to ensure the quality level of the internal communication coordination are described in WP5 “Project coordination”, Deliverable (D) 5.1 “Project Handbook”.

Digital4Planet, as Task 4.1 (“Dissemination and Communication”) leader, will closely cooperate with the Project Coordinator, Martel, to ensure efficient, fluent, and controlled communication among all the partners throughout the project. This is also ensured by the ongoing bi-monthly General Assembly (GA) meetings, during which all partners gather to exchange updates and best practices on their activities and align on the guidance and updates on the communication and dissemination efforts.

3.3 ONLINE COMMUNICATION

3.3.1 Website

An initial page with the most relevant tabs, including a description of the project, its goals, the consortium partners, and the SNS JU was launched in Month (M) 02 (February 2024). The contact email, newsletter subscription, and links to social media channels to raise awareness about the start of the project and engage the visitors in the upcoming activities, were also included on the website.

In M04, April 2024, a fully functional website (www.6g4society.eu) with the added tabs for news, scientific publications, public deliverables, events, and an introduction to the citizens’ survey was launched. Web design experts within the project consortium conceived its design and structure to promote the outcomes to the relevant target groups.

The website is intended to provide a one-stop hub for the presentation and promotion of the project’s activities and to this end, several measures have already been implemented, namely:

- Gather email addresses of interested users thanks to a subscription form available on all pages. This mailing list will help us spread the activities of the project through a periodic e-Newsletter and digital digest. This mailing list will also support the spreading of the citizens’ survey as it is launched, and a reminder to fill it out will also be sent to the mailing list.
- Encourage partners to submit their news related to 6G4S to the project website for republishing to the broader audience. This will strengthen the website’s relevance, as well as increase its reach and impact.
- Encourage partners to repost news of direct and indirect interest from partners and the general media. This shows that 6G4S is involved and engaged in the larger world. If possible, this content should be posted with added commentary that demonstrates expertise and adds value to the article.
- Organise and aggregate news articles by topic and relevance to improve the ability to share e.g., via social channels, especially when dealing with calls to action such as participation to events. This allows the project to maximise the value of its communication outreach.

The project website serves as a comprehensive platform to assess the effectiveness of 6G4S communication and dissemination efforts. This is achieved by carefully analysing web analytics data. The 6G4S consortium utilises [Matomo](#) as their web analytics software platform to obtain detailed reports on the project’s communication campaigns, website visits, acquisitions, and overall website performance. Importantly, Matomo aligns with European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) standards and safeguards the ownership of collected data.

The following figure shows the analytics of the website visits since launching the website. It shows that there has been a total of 118 visits to the website, with 258 page views. A more detailed breakdown can also be found in the following Figure.

FIGURE 3: 6G4S' WEBSITE ANALYTICS

The project website's home page has evolved into a clear and clean communication interface that is easily navigable, giving access to all relevant public information about the project. The website is structured into the following sections:

FIGURE 4: OVERVIEW OF THE WEBSITE STRUCTURE

FIGURE 5: 6G4SOCIETY HOMEPAGE

3.3.2 Social media channels and hashtags

Various social media channels have been established as marketing tools in order to promote activities and outputs of the project on a regular basis, while also encouraging a wider discussion on the topics related to the project such as sustainability in tech or Key Value Indicators (KVI)s). Thus, 6G4S created an active presence on the most popular social media channels, such as LinkedIn and X (former Twitter), as well as Mastodon in an active attempt to promote open-source and decentralised internet platforms and thus, pro-actively contributing to 6G4S' project objectives. These platforms are all linked to the website. You will find below a brief description of the 6G4S approach to each social media channel.

3.3.2.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is currently the main business network in the world and has over 1 billion users in more than 200 countries and territories¹. In preparation for the project's Kick-Off meeting, 6G4S set up its LinkedIn account (January 2024), and in the first four months since the inception of the project, it has gained 141 followers, with a total of 287 reactions and 13 reposts to the content that has been shared so far.

The LinkedIn profile of 6G4S is a complement to the website, helps drive traffic to 6g4society.eu, and provides a way to promote the project. We will mention partners' LinkedIn pages when appropriate to create a positive exchange about visibility. We plan to engage the other initiatives and projects in the SNS JU ecosystem while promoting 6G4S's activities in the relevant LinkedIn groups with a direct link to the project's page, to further increase the social media audience and diversify the user base of the page by targeting more vertical representatives/managers.

Appropriate hashtags and accounts were identified to maximise the reach and coverage of the 6G4S LinkedIn channel for the project's content to be found by the target audience, to increase the number of views, likes and shares, and to increase the number of visitors to the website.

3.3.2.2 X

X is a dynamic social network that spreads news in real-time on a global scale. In preparation for the project's Kick-Off meeting, 6G4S set up its X account @6G4S (January 2024), and in the first four months since the inception of the project, it has gained 37 followers. 18 posts have been tweeted since then, reporting on the project's Kick-Off, the project's attendance at events and the publishing of the first digital digest.

The X account is used for promoting and disseminating the development of 6G4S, including news, events, outcomes, etc. Moreover, re-tweets are made of relevant and interesting content from sources, the main being SNS JU, to strengthen the synergies within the ecosystem (and thus supporting the work in WP3 as well). Last but not least, by following relevant users, 6G4S not only gains access to more relevant content and updates, but also acquires more followers.

6G4S uses X to make meaningful connections with active and relevant audiences (EC and relevant Directorates-General (DGs), policymakers, industry stakeholders, and the general public). These connections can result in opportunities for the project across the stakeholder network. It also serves as a tool to inform everyone in real-time on what is happening during project's workshops, attended events, and other relevant activities of the project.

Appropriate hashtags and accounts were identified to maximise the reach and coverage of the 6G4S X channel for the project's content to be found by the target audience, to increase the number of views, likes and shares, and to increase the number of visitors to the website.

3.3.2.3 Mastodon

Mastodon is a decentralised social media platform that allows users to connect and communicate with others through microblogging in a federated network of independently operated servers. It offers greater control over privacy, fosters community building, and promotes a diverse and inclusive online environment.

Because 6G4S aims to embed societal and sustainable values into the development of 6G technologies, it is essential for the project itself to proactively support open-source and decentralised internet platforms. Furthermore, the EC has clearly declared its wish to move away from only working with big tech company platforms, and following the trend of other tech-related CSAs such as Next Generation Internet, 6G4S has opened its Mastodon account in February 2024: @6g4society@eupolicy.social.

Being a newer social media platform and therefore being less known, 6G4S' strategy is to use LinkedIn and X to highlight the Mastodon account and drive followers there. In terms of content, the posts will resemble the ones on X, highlighting the main updates, events, and activities from the 6G4S consortium.

3.3.2.4 YouTube

YouTube is an online video-sharing and social media platform. It will serve as the main channel to communicate 6G4S' video content such as interviews with experts or interviews with partners.

6G4S set up its YouTube account @6G4SOCIETY in February 2024, and since posting its first video has gathered nine subscribers. All videos posted on the YouTube channel will be cross-promoted on the project's other social media channels. A screenshot of the first video on the YouTube channel can be found in Section 3.4.3.3.

3.3.2.5 Hashtags and relevant handles

TABLE 3: 6G4S RELATED HASHTAGS, LINKEDIN, X AND MASTODON HANDLES

6G4S RELATED HASHTAGS, LINKEDIN, X AND MASTODON HANDLES	
Hashtags	#6G, #6G4S, #6G4Society #SNS, #6GSNS #EURResearch, #HorizonEU #FutureConnectivity #SocietalValues, #GreenTech, #SustainableTech, #TechForGood
LinkedIn handles	Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) European Commission 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association EU Digital & Tech EU Science, Research and Innovation
X handles	@6G_SNS @EU_Commission @HorizonEU @DigitalEU @ITU @one6GGlobal
Mastodon handle	@6g4society@eupolicy.social

6G4S partners' X and LinkedIn accounts will be handled in relevant posts to maximise the social media outreach.

TABLE 4: SOCIAL MEDIA HANDLES OF 6G4S PARTNERS

Partner name	LinkedIn handle	X handle
Martel Innovate	Martel Innovate	@Martel_Innovate
Cyber Ethics Lab.	Cyber Ethics Lab.	@CyberethicsLab

NOVA		NOVA		@NovaGreece
Public Communication (PSCE)	Safety Europe	Public Communication (PSCE)	Safety Europe	@psc_e
eBOS		eBOS		eBOS
Digital for Planet		Digital for Planet		@Digital4Planet

A dedicated section of the digital digest will be reserved for the consortium partner interviews, where readers can learn more about the organisations driving the project, what their role is, and how they believe 6G4S will impact European society.

3.3.3 News items and digital digest

The News section on the website is being populated with news items related to the latest project updates and relevant events, with the aim of informing the users and target audience and utilize key words to drive traffic and engagement to the 6G4S website.

The news items, as well as relevant events and announcements, will be summarized and collected into a digital digest that will be posted approximately every three months in a dedicated space on the website. An e-mail that links directly to the digital digest will be sent out to the addresses collected through the mailing list. More specifically, the digest will provide regular updates on trends of 6G and sustainability in tech innovation practices, project findings and results, and news from the consortium partners, among others. The Newsletters will also contain information regarding the upcoming tasks and events in an attempt to inform the audience on how they can get in touch with the project and the connected initiatives. The citizens' survey and the information packages will also be shared through the digital digest.

A typical digital digest of the project will contain highlights (major outcomes, links, contacts, and dissemination activities), the most important news, announcements, and a schedule of the major upcoming events. Mailings with invitations to relevant workshops and webinars, consultations, and other information that cannot wait for the digest publication or that cannot appear only in the digest, will be sent out regularly to the same database used for the digest. Project partners will provide information for the digest and ensure that the content is accurate, and a specific section will be reserved for the consortium partner interviews where readers can learn more about the organisations driving the project, what their role is, and how they believe 6G4S will impact European society.

The first issue of the digest has been published in April 2024 (M04). An internal calendar will be shared with all project partners to receive their contributions and the final approval about the content and appearance. A registration functionality allowing the interested visitors to subscribe to the digest is already available on the project website. It will also be ensured that all actions comply with the requirements of the GDPR.

3.3.4 Press releases

A first press release for the 6G-NTN kick-off meeting was drafted in a designed press release template (see Appendix B) to ensure a consistent look and feel across all the consortium's communication with the press. It was released on 13 February 2024.

For the next months of project's activities, press releases will be edited on a regular basis to correspond with key accomplishments (e.g., organisation of a large event, implementation of key activities within the project, etc.). Using targeted media databases and specialised software such as [Prowly](#) and [Meltwater](#), press releases will be published in national and European media. In the paragraph below, a first target list is presented. 6G4S also plans to target specific publications and media outlets relevant to its area of interest, vertical domains, and stakeholders to promote the work carried out by the project. All partners will also be in charge of communicating with their local media outlets.

A preliminary list includes:

- 🔄 EU-funded research and innovation (i.e., Science Business, EU Research).
- 🔄 European and national outlets (e.g., Euronews, The Parliament Magazine, Politico EU, The Guardian, Sonntagszeitung, Le Temps, BBC Click, The Huffington Post, La Stampa, Euronews.next).
- 🔄 Green technology and general tech news outlets (e.g., BusinessGreen, Environment Journal, Tech Crunch, Guardian Tech).

Furthermore, significant project developments, news and announcements, white papers and articles introducing 6G4S will be published on third-party portals, including professional and specialised platforms, relevant thematic blogs and collaboration platforms, partners' web portals, as well as through several freely accessible tools.

A preliminary list of the freely accessible portals includes:

- 🔄 Cordis projects & results: <http://cordis.europa.eu/projects/homeen.html>
- 🔄 Horizon Magazine <http://horizon-magazine.eu/>
- 🔄 Headlines on the Commission's Research & Innovation website www.ec.europa.eu/research/infocentre/allheadlinesen.cfm
- 🔄 CORDIS Wire <http://cordis.europa.eu/wire/>

Furthermore, to ensure a wider reach, all partners will be responsible for engaging with their local media outlets. The project's website will host all press releases.

3.4 OFFLINE COMMUNICATION

3.4.1 Events, workshops and conferences

Events, workshops and conferences represent important networking opportunities for 6G4S, where both the vision of the project can be communicated to others as well as potential collaboration opportunities with other actors are cultivated.

By the time of publishing this deliverable, the following events, workshops and conferences have been attended by 6G4S:

- 🔄 Mobile World Congress (MWC) (26 February 2024 to 29 February 2024): 6G4S attended MWC and started its first physical networking activities with other attendees. Furthermore, 6G4S was present at the SNS JU's session "6G Horizon: Bridging perspectives for a sustainable future". The participation of 6G4S was published on the project's social media platforms and a video interview was taken during the event (see Section 3.4.3.3).

- SNS JU Webinar to introduce Call 2 projects (14 March 2024): 6G4S presented its vision, goals and planned activities in front of around 50 participants. The participation of 6G4S was published on the project’s social media platforms.
- ETSI Conference on “Non-Terrestrial Networks, a Native Component of 6G” (3 April 2024 to 4 April 2024): 6G4S attended this conference and networked with other SNS JU projects.

FIGURE 6: 6G4S PROJECT COORDINATOR PRESENTING AT SNS JU'S WEBINAR ON 14 MARCH 2024

At the time of publishing this deliverable, 6G4S plans on attending the following events, workshops, and conferences:

- 20×30: Europe’s Advanced Digital Skills Summit (16 May 2024): 6G4S will be hosting a stand to promote the citizens’ survey which will have just launched. This summit is also an important space to reach networks outside of the SNS JU. The participation will be promoted on the project’s social media channels and the digital digest.
- 6G Global Summit (21 May to 22 May 2024): 6G4S plans to attend sessions and network with peers in between sessions.
- EuCNC & 6G Summit (3 June 2024 to 6 June 2024): 6G4S will be organising a special session in collaboration with [FIDAL](#) and [BroadEU.net](#). The title is “Towards a sustainable and socially accepted 6G for society” with the goals of engaging 6G stakeholders to participate in the conversation about societal and sustainability main challenges and priorities, presenting the work and activities of the three projects and gathering input and feedback from the participants on the perception of 6G related to the topics of the environment, health, and KVIs. The participation will be promoted on the project’s social media channels and the digital digest.

- Public Safety Communications Europe Forum (4 June 2024 to 5 June 2024): 6G4S will be hosting a poster session at the PSCE Forum. The aim is to present the project's vision, goals and activities, as well as first results. The participation will be promoted on the project's social media channels and the digital digest.
- International European Society for Ecological Economics (ESEE) - Degrowth Conference (18 June to 21 June 2024): 6G4S plans to attend sessions and network with peers in between sessions.
- Digital With Purpose Global Summit (9 July to 11 July 2024): 6G4S plans to attend sessions and network with peers in between sessions.
- 1st International Workshop on Value-driven Ethical Networking in 6G (ETHICNET) co-located with IEEE (Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers) International Symposium on Personal, Indoor and Mobile Radio Communications 2024 (2 September to 5 September 2024): 6G4S has submitted a paper within the context of the conference.
- Various ETSI conferences.

6G4S will participate to relevant events, workshops, and conferences throughout the course of the project.

3.4.2 Publications

The 6G4S partners have set a target of publishing four scientific publications in journals, and four scientific publications in conference papers. Table 2 below presents the relevant publications which will be submitted. We expect this list to be further reviewed and populated in the upcoming months as the academic and research partners take a deeper dive into the 6G4S results, methodologies, and challenges, which may be relevant to the scientific community. All scientific publications issued by the consortium will be made available through the website of the project, where a specific section has already been created.

TABLE 5: PLANNED SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS (STAND: APRIL 2024)

Title/Topic	Conference or Journal
Towards a sustainable and socially accepted 6G for society	EuCNC 2024
Challenges of the industry: KPIs/KVIs, sustainability, Vision	SNS Journal
KVI definitions and categories paper	1st International Workshop on Value-driven Ethical Networking in 6G (ETHICNET)

3.4.3 Promotional materials

3.4.3.1 Flyers

Project flyers will be created and used to inform interested people about the project's objectives and activities. Upon completion, the flyers will be uploaded to the 6G4S website and shared as printed versions during relevant events.

FIGURE 7: MOCKUP OF 6G4S FLYERS

3.4.3.2 Roll-ups and posters

Roll-ups will be created, matching the look and feel of the website and the overall project design concept to meet the needs of the project. 6G4S will also consider producing event-focused posters, if necessary, where the content of the poster will be replaced to fit the needs and theme of the event.

Both the roll-ups and the posters will be prepared in English (local languages to be considered if appropriate or necessary) to raise awareness of the stakeholders and a variety of relevant audiences about the project with succinct textual and graphical information. Printable versions of the posters will also be created and provided to partners to be printed and used at the events they participate in. The design will be easily adjustable to the requirements individual partners have, in case an additional or a more specific version is required. The project logo, the EU flag & acknowledgment along with the 6G4S website and the social media links will be displayed on all promotional materials.

3.4.3.3 Videos

6G4S will produce and release ten videos to present the project and its achievements. The videos will serve as a visual platform for viewers to learn more about the project's vision, goals, activities, and results. All videos will be uploaded to the project's [YouTube channel](#). An initial video presenting what 6G4Society is about and how sustainability is shaping the development and deployment of 6G was posted in February 2024.

FIGURE 8: 6G4S' VIDEO "WHAT IS 6G4SOCIETY?"

3.4.4 Promotion of citizens' survey

Aiming to get 1,000 respondents, the 6G4S citizens' survey is an essential pillar of the project as it will serve as the main tool to gather the public's perception of 5G and 6G as well as their wants and fears related to 6G. The survey will be distributed and promoted through the project's social media channels and the digital digest. 6G4S will also engage the other projects within the SNS JU network to promote it within their circles through their social media channels, newsletters, and mailing lists.

Citizens associations and universities will be contacted to promote the survey within their networks. Targeting these actors will allow for a broad range of socio-demographic groups to be reached (young students through universities e.g.). Furthermore, the possibility of presenting the project and promoting the survey through a project stand, posters, flyers, or a class shout will be explored with the universities contacted.

A specific flyer as well as a sticker with a QR code leading straight to the survey will be designed and distributed at relevant events, workshops, and conferences. A QR code will be integrated at the end of the 6G4S general presentation so that any time a partner presents the project, they can lead the participants to the survey.

FIGURE 9: MOCKUP OF STICKERS FOR THE 6G4S CITIZENS' SURVEY

Deliverable 2.1. “Public engagement strategy and plan” will explain more in-depth how the survey will be designed and promoted.

3.4.5 Information package and its promotion

One of the final products for 6G4S is the creation of an explanatory information package for non-experts. This package aims to foster a better understanding of the potential societal, environmental, and public health effects of 6G and related technologies, and to make the public audience aware of benefits, opportunities, and risks related to 6G technology-wide deployment. The information package will include info sheets, videos, and infographics.

The information package will be distributed and promoted through the project’s social media channels and the digital digest. 6G4S will also engage the other projects within the SNS JU network to promote it within their circles through their social media channels, newsletters, and mailing lists.

4 SYNERGIES WITH SNS JU AND OTHER RELEVANT PROJECTS AND INITIATIVES

6G4S being an integral part of the SNS JU ecosystem, the following section delves into the synergies that will be cultivated within SNS JU as well as other relevant initiatives to amplify the project's message and grow its reach and relevance.

4.1 SNS JU

4.1.1 Stakeholder mapping

6G4S is committed to establishing synergies with various stakeholders and initiatives, aligning with the SNS JU and other relevant networks. Stakeholders such as policymakers, financing bodies, standardization organizations, and open-source groups will be engaged to ensure comprehensive coverage of perspectives. Moreover, collaboration with SNS projects and their members, the SNS JU Office, the SNS JU Governing Board, and the 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA) will facilitate knowledge exchange and coordination efforts. By leveraging existing work and establishing proper coordination, the project aims to identify links with international and European authorities, committees, and working groups on issues of acceptability, inclusiveness, security, and sustainability of next-generation smart networks and services. Additionally, the project will scout additional strategic initiatives to build synergies and explore opportunities for collaboration. Priority targets include running and future SNS projects under streams A, B, C, and D, with a focus on validating the Technology Acceptance Model, engaging stakeholders, and addressing cross-cutting topics such as KVIs and Key Sustainability Indicators (KSIs). Furthermore, the project will position itself within relevant Working Groups (WGs), proposing the establishment of new groups, if necessary, to contribute to discussions and share insights on technology acceptance models and sustainability indicators for 6G technology.

The ongoing stakeholder mapping of the SNS ecosystem aims to identify key entities for engagement, and also extends to include policymakers, financing bodies, standardization organisations, and open-source groups. The project is strategically liaising with SNS working groups and 6G-IA associate member activities (for example, the project has been engaging with the Societal Challenges WG, currently a sub-group of the Vision WG). The mapping is also leveraging insights from the 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5GPPP) ecosystem. Additionally, the project extensively maps KVI linkages in the 63 ongoing SNS CSAs and projects to identify which has existing links and gaps. To date, it is clear that at least 10 SNS projects explicitly mention KVIs in publicly available materials. Engagement strategies and an outreach timeline are being developed to liaise with these projects, including questions to ask, as well as with 5G/6G industry and research, including network providers, technology developers, Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), research institutes, and complementary industries. Moreover, the project will explore complementary projects outside the SNS ecosystem at national, European, and international levels, as well as liaise with 5G/6G verticals and related associations (see Section 4.2.).

6G4Society Stakeholder Mapping

Includes all stakeholders involved in technological development around 5G/6G, as well as stakeholder primarily involved in the provisioning of the enabled services

FIGURE 10: 6G4S STAKEHOLDER MAPPING

4.1.2 SNS Communication Task Force

SNS JU has a Communication Task Force that groups all Communication Managers from the SNS JU projects. The Task Force meets online once a month and discusses the latest communication activities happening in their project, how they are currently collaborating with others from the ecosystem and what sort of communication support is needed. 6G4S uses this platform to network and stay up to date with the latest communication plans of the SNS projects and promote relevant activities such as workshops or the citizens’ survey.

4.1.3 SNS JU Journal

Every year, the SNS JU publishes a journal that presents its portfolio of research, innovation, and trial projects. The document gives an overview of the current projects the SNS JU funds, what they aim to achieve, and what activities have been implemented. 6G4S has submitted an entry for the 2024 version, which will be published later this year. A first scientific publication titled “Challenges of the industry: KPIs/KVIs, sustainability, Vision” was also submitted in March 2024 (see Table 2).

This publication is an important channel to learn about what other SNS JU initiatives have been working on as well as present 6G4S to the rest of the ecosystem, its vision, activities and results.

4.1.4 SNS Webinars

The SNS JU regularly organises webinars to promote collaboration between the network’s projects and foster discussions on topics important to 6G technology and its development. 6G4S aims to join as many webinars as possible, either as a participant or an active contributor. 6G4S has already participated in an SNS JU webinar in March 2024, as described in Section 3.4.1.

4.2 OTHER RELEVANT INITIATIVES

6G4S will engage with complementary national, European, and global organisations and peer associations through various means of outreach (e.g., email correspondence, conference attendance, working group meetings, etc.). This includes collaborating with industry and SMEs involved in 6G innovation, establishing partnerships with European peers, and fostering relationships with international associations in vertical sectors. Additionally, the project will participate in various European 6G initiatives and engage with Member State initiatives at national and regional levels to ensure alignment with broader objectives. Such initiatives are currently being mapped, focusing first, on the project partner countries. The project will also explore synergies with Universities, higher education institutions (HEI), Research Institutions, and Non-profit technology centres, especially through conferences and workshops. To access vertical stakeholders and value drivers, the project will connect with telecom organisations such as ESA, ECSSO, ETNO, and GSMA, among others. It will also establish links with international entities like 5G Americas, 5GForum Korea, and IMT-2020 & IMT-2030 China, among others. Furthermore, complementary domain associations including IoT, Big Data, Software, Photonics, Microelectronics, Robotics, Aviation, and Space, will be engaged to leverage expertise and resources. The project will explore collaboration opportunities with initiatives like EUREKA Cluster, Digital Europe, and CORE, among others, to expand its reach, and maximise impact.

5 PERFORMANCE ASSESSMENT

The following section presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) related to communication and dissemination, the deliverables and the milestones, as well as a risk assessment and mitigation strategy.

5.1 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION KPIS

The 6G4S project defined a comprehensive set of Communication and Dissemination KPIs to monitor the results achieved. They are illustrated in the table below.

TABLE 6: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION KPIS

Name	Indicator	Target number	Number at M04
Scientific publications to journals	Number of scientific publications	4	0
Scientific publications to conference papers	Number of scientific publications	4	2
Scientific workshops attended/organised	Number of scientific workshops	4	0
6G4S website unique visitors	N. of website unique visitors to 6G4S website	> 50,000	118
Social media followers	N. of followers on LinkedIn, X and Mastodon	> 5,000	192
Flyers / posters / rollups and other promotional materials	N. of promotional materials done	4	0
Download of policy roadmap, papers, information packages, etc.	N. of downloads of documents on the 6G4S website	> 1,000	N/A
Digital Digest	N. of digital digests	8	1

Expert interviews / animated graphic videos	N. of videos published on the YouTube channel	>10	1
Citizen's survey	N. of respondents	> 1,000	N/A
Participation in citizens' events and presentations	N. of citizen events / presentations attended	> 15	0
Organisation of Citizens / Policy Makers Forum	N. of participants	> 200	N/A

5.2 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION DELIVERABLES AND MILESTONES

The 6G4S project defined a set of Communication and Dissemination deliverables and milestones. They are illustrated in the table below.

TABLE 7: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION DELIVERABLES

Number	Title	Submission month
D4.1	Communication and Dissemination Strategy and Plan	M04
D4.2	Communication and Dissemination Report	M24

TABLE 8: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION MILESTONES

Number	Milestone name	Submission month
1	Setup and Handover with running 6G-SNS CSAs	M06
2	SSH Knowledge-base created	M09
3	First events and engagement results	M12
4	Public events and Stakeholders' Positions	M18
5	Sustainability and Technology Acceptance	M24
6	Project Closure and Handover with new 6G-SNS CSAs	M24

5.3 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION RISK ASSESSMENT

The 6G4S project defined various potential risks related to communication and dissemination and how to mitigate them. They are illustrated in the table below.

TABLE 9: COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION POTENTIAL RISKS AND MITIGATION

Potential risk	Mitigation strategy
Interoperability issues with project outcomes hinder their adoption.	6G4S will build its outcomes on top of results from running SNS JU projects, and it will identify a common framework to be used by all of them and future initiatives. Moreover, participation in 6G-IA and standardisation WGs will also address this risk.
Dissemination and knowledge transfer might not reach a critical mass of users in order to take up, adopt, and exploit the results and products of the project.	The communication experience of all consortium partners and the network of international connections (including those with 6G-IA initiatives) will ensure wide dissemination. The activity will be constantly trialled and measured.
Lack of volunteers during engagement campaigns.	The consortium partners will make use of their professional and personal networks to spread the word and cross-promote 6G4S content. Collaborations with different actors (such as universities and citizens' associations) will be cultivated.
Gather biased feeds during engagement campaigns.	A big focus will be put on using unbiased language. A pilot community to test out the citizens' survey will be asked for feedback on whether the language is biased. Native speakers from the consortium partners will be asked to re-read the translations of the survey to check the language.
Lack of interest from 6G-IA projects and initiatives to collaborate and adopt.	A win-win collaboration with the network will be fostered.
Dissemination and knowledge transfer might not reach a critical mass of users in order to take up, adopt, and exploit.	6G4S will put an emphasis on attending events, networking with peers and cultivating win-win collaboration with synergy partners.
Partner leaves the consortium.	Regular GAs and F2F meetings as well as cross-WPs meetings ensure a bond and trust between the partners. Furthermore, all six partners have large networks that could

	be tapped into if a back-up partner is needed.
Key milestones or deliverables are delayed.	An internal process has been put in place for the review of the deliverables whereas first the table of contents, then 50%, and then 100% of the content is shared for internal review over several weeks. Furthermore, a list of the deliverables and milestones is at the beginning of the bi-weekly GA agenda.
Lack of alignment between WPs. Potential or synergies not exploited.	Regular GAs and F2F meetings as well as cross-WPs meetings ensure a bond and trust between the partners. Furthermore, transparent internal communication on WP activities and deliverables is being emphasised so that all partners can collaborate where wanted and needed.
Lack of compliance with ethics, regulatory constraints and social expectations.	One of the deliverables is linked to ethics, thus a certain amount of monitoring on this aspect is being done.

6 CONCLUSIONS AND NEXT STEPS

Deliverable 4.1, Dissemination and Communication Strategy and Plan, has been developed to provide guidelines and a consistent framework for all planned project activities to ensure 6G4S's broad visibility, adequate promotion, and uptake of its results. The document at hand presents the initial communication and dissemination strategy, describes activities already conducted between M01 and M04, and outlines the planned promotional activities for the coming months. Developing this strategy at the early stages of the project will allow 6G4S to maximise the impact of communication and dissemination activities, and sustain the concepts, achievements, and knowledge developed throughout the project.

The goal of this strategy and plan is to guarantee that:

- 🔄 All outreach activities follow the guidelines and are executed within the planned schedule.
- 🔄 The messages are consistent and of a high standard.
- 🔄 All consortium members contribute to promoting the project.

This deliverable constitutes a handbook for all project partners which guarantees a harmonised approach when setting up and performing communication and dissemination activities, as it lists all stakeholders, communication channels, dissemination activities, and corresponding KPIs. It also addresses the European Commission and SNS JU, essential partners in the realisation of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy and Plan.

A monitoring and evaluation framework has been defined to measure the achieved progress and impact of the proposed strategy. Project deliverable D4.2 will provide details on the progress of the strategy, achieved KPIs, attended and organised events, and the effectiveness of 6G4S's online presence at M18 and M24.

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APPENDIX A: 6G4S BRAND GUIDELINES

What Is a Brand Identity?

A distinctive brand identity serves as a beacon, ensuring a unified presence across various platforms, be it digital or in print. It shapes the perception of those who engage with the brand, leaving a lasting impression and shaping their understanding of it.

Outlined herein are the guiding principles and visual elements that define the essence of the 6G4Society project. These directives are designed to aid in the creation and curation of visual representations that embody its identity.

Illustrations of the 6G4Society brand identity can be witnessed across diverse channels such as LinkedIn and Twitter, showcasing its unique character and resonance.

Logo

Main version of the 6G4Society logo with some basic recommendations.

Main version - Horizontal

6G4SOCIETY

Main version - Compact

6G⁴SOCIETY

Icon version (for social media & apps)

6G⁴S

Safe area

Minimum size

© 2024 | 6G4Society

3

Logo Variations

The main logo is also provided in the variations depicted here below, to allow readability over dark backgrounds or for black and white printing purposes.

Greyscale version

6G4SOCIETY

Negative version

6G4SOCIETY

Black&White version

6G4SOCIETY

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4

Dos and Dont's

Basic instructions on how to use the main logo - and its variations - over different types of backgrounds.

Dos

Negative version on high contrasted background.

Main version on background assuring high contrast.

Don'ts

Not enough contrasted background.

Not enough contrasted background.

© 2024 | 6G4Society

5

Corporate Colours

A main palette consisting of 6 colors, 2 of which are derived from the SNS JU brand guidelines, ecosystem to which 6g4society belongs.

For slide presentations and deliverables: the colour of standard elements has been defined and locked in the respective templates, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments.

To change colours (icons or additional text), editors will find the corporate color palette in the templates.

Dos

C69 M20 Y0 K15
R67 G174 B217
#43AED9

C69 M20 Y0 K35
R51 G133 B166
#3385A6

C69 M20 Y0 K55
R36 G92 B115
#245C73

C67 M12 Y0 K65
R29 G78 B89
#1D4E59

C55 M58 Y0 K66
R39 G36 B86
#272456

C50 M9 Y0 K5
R121 G220 B242
#79DCF2

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6

Font Types

6G4Society's brand uses **Mundial (Bold version)** for headings and **Mundial (Thin and Semi Bold versions)** for body copy and subtitles. The usage of other versions of the fonts are allowed. This applies to the all promotional material. On the 6G4Society's website the **Google Font Outfit** is used in various weights.

For deliverables, the system font **Arial (only Regular and Bold versions)** should be used instead, to avoid missing font issues, as those documents are likely to be mainly edited outside design departments. It could be used also for presentations in case the two brand fonts are missing.

Headings

(website, presentations, and all promotional materials)

Mundial Bold
ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
1234567890

Body copy - subtitles

(website, presentations, and all promotional materials)

Mundial Thin
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Mundial Semi Bold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Alternative body copy and headings

(for deliverables and presentations)

Arial regular
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

Arial Bold
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz 1234567890

EU Recognition

For Publications

All the EC funded projects under Horizon Europe don't need anymore to clearly show the acknowledgement to the EC fund in all Dissemination & Communication materials.

The following disclaimer MUST be used with the EU flag into scientific publications / press releases / blogs / deliverables (where there are author, where opinions/editorial/comments/conclusions are stated..). Project's acronym and Grant Agreement number could be add only as shown here below. This disclaimer should be used in the website footer too.

6G4SOCIETY project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101139070. This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI).

For Promo Materials

For merchandising or any other promo materials (bookmarks / roll-up / flyers / posters) that usually report only vision / phases / objectives, the disclaimer is not mandatory, but then **MUST be used the EU emblem / recognition**, as shown here below.

Contacts

For any questions regarding the 6G4Society graphic assets and the uses you would like to make of them, do not hesitate to contact Matilde Voltolini from Digital for Planet:
matilde.voltolini@digital4planet.org

All 6G4Society graphic assets, including this brand guidelines and the font, can be downloaded on the repository of the project.

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 Co-funded by the European Union **6GSNS**

6G4Society project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

APPENDIX B: 6G4S 1ST PRESS RELEASE

**March 2024
Press Release**

6G4Society Project Sets the Stage for Human-Centric Next-Generation Networks

In the fast-paced realm of telecommunications, the race to define the future of connectivity has accelerated with the advent of 6G technology. Seizing the moment, the 6G4Society project, a pioneering Horizon Europe Coordination and Supporting Action, officially launched its operations in January 2024. The project emerges as a beacon of innovation, set to revolutionize the landscape of 6G technology development.

As the world eagerly awaits the transformative capabilities of 6G, 6G4Society recognizes the critical need to redefine the narrative, ensuring that the evolution of technology aligns with the betterment of society.

The initiative sets out to engage all key stakeholders within the Smart Networks and Services (SNS) ecosystem. This broad spectrum of involvement extends beyond industry players to include civil society, regulators, policy makers, media, and the public at large.

The 6G4Society project adopts an inclusive approach to guarantee that accurate and transparent information about the expected impacts of 6G technology is disseminated. By fostering a collective understanding of the implications of 6G, the project aims to empower stakeholders to actively contribute to shaping the future of telecommunications.

The 6G4Society project stands as a testament to the commitment of Horizon Europe to drive innovation that aligns with societal values. Through collaboration with leading experts, industry visionar-

ies, and the wider community, the project aspires to not only push the boundaries of technological achievement but also to set a new standard for responsible innovation. By addressing the complex interplay between technology and society, the project aims to establish a blueprint for the ethical and sustainable deployment of 6G technology.

The consortium takes pride in its broad spectrum of skills and competencies, spanning across disciplines such as Social Sciences and Humanities with contributions from the Cyber Ethics Lab and PSCE, technological expertise provided by NOVA and eBOS, proficient networking coordination and management led by Martel Innovate, and effective communication and engagement skills exemplified by Digital for Planet. This diverse array of capabilities guarantees the adoption of a comprehensive approach to address the complex challenges inherent in the development of 6G technology.

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Co-funded by
the European Union

6GSNS

Project funded by

European Union
Horizon Europe
Coordination and Supporting Action
6G4SOCIETY

Swiss State
Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation
SERI

6G4SOCIETY project has received funding from the Smart Networks and Services Joint Undertaking (SNS JU) under the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101015070. This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)

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ⁱ LinkedIn (n.d.). About LinkedIn. Retrieved April 2, 2024, from <https://about.linkedin.com/>